

**DETERMINATION OF CHARACTERISTICS FOR THE FORMATION OF
REQUIREMENTS STREAMS IN THE SYSTEM OF MAINTENANCE AND REPAIR OF
MACHINES**

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Abstract: *In the service system, the main element is the incoming flow of requirements. The flow of requirements for maintenance and repair is a random process consisting of flows of homogeneous and heterogeneous events that occur at random intervals. The time intervals between receipts of claims may be subject to different distribution laws.*

The parameter, requirements arriving per unit of time (λ_k) for maintenance is a static expression of the average daily amount of the incoming flow of requirements (N_c) into the maintenance and repair system per day ($\lambda_{ki} = N_{ci}$):

The obtained parameters indicate the need to take into account possible fluctuations in the flow of requirements in the design and organization of maintenance and repair systems.

Keywords: *reliability, queuing system, demand flow, maintenance, repair, random factors, events, recovery process, probabilistic properties, intensity, failure.*

In any queuing system, the main element is the incoming flow of requirements. The flow of requirements for maintenance and repair is formed as an objective reality as a result of the impact on the objects of operation of various random factors that reduce their reliability.

Scientific research devoted to the reliability of technical systems [1,2, 3, 4, 5] shows that the flow of requirements is a random process consisting of flows of homogeneous and heterogeneous events that occur at random intervals. The time intervals between receipts of claims may be subject to different distribution laws.

However, as shown in works [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7] on queuing theories, that it is quite correct to use the steady simplest flow in applied studies, in which the

probability of arrival at time intervals t exactly k requirements is described by the Poisson law:

$$P_k(t) = \frac{(\lambda_k \cdot t)^k}{k!} \cdot e^{-\lambda_k \cdot t} \quad (1)$$

where λ_k - is the demand flow density (flow parameter).

The simplest flow has three main properties: stationarity, absence of consequences and ordinaryness, which characterizes it as one of the most intense discrete flows.

Poisson's law is central to queuing theory. This special position is due to several reasons. First, it has simplifying analytical and probabilistic properties. Second, in many cases the sum of a large number of independent stationary renewal processes (each with an arbitrary distribution of renewal times) converges to a Poisson process. Thirdly, the queuing system, designed with the simplest flow in mind, is placed in advance in more stressful conditions. A system designed for the implementation of such a flow makes it possible to serve other random flows of requirements with the same density of their receipt more reliably [2, 7].

As shown by studies of the reliability of vehicles (cars) and agricultural machinery [2,4, 6, 8], the time intervals between failures obey the exponential distribution law. The algorithm of work [10] proved the relationship between the Poisson law and the exponential distribution. Therefore, when characterizing a probabilistic process in queuing systems, one usually considers a Poisson flow of requirements, which is described by an exponential distribution of time intervals between requirements.

One of the main characteristics of the demand flow is its intensity, which is defined as the mathematical expectation of the number of demands arriving per unit of time. In time intervals $(0, t)$ the mathematical expectation is equal to

$$M_t[k] = e^{-\lambda_k \cdot t} \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k \cdot \frac{(\lambda_k \cdot t)^k}{k!} = \lambda_k \cdot t \quad (2)$$

Hence, the mathematical expectation of the number of claims arriving per unit time ($t=1$) is equal to

$$M_t[k] = \lambda_k \quad (3)$$

The parameter, claims arriving per unit of time (λ_k) is a static expression of the average daily number of claims of the i -th type of maintenance and repairs- N_c . Then the parameters of the incoming flow of requirements to the maintenance and repair system per day will be:

$$M_k[k] = \lambda_{ki} = N_{ci}; \quad D[k]_i = \lambda_{ki}; \quad \sigma[k] = \sqrt{N_c}, \quad (4)$$

where $D[k]_i$ - is the demand flow dispersion; $\sigma[k]_i$ - standard deviation.

Consideration of these parameters leads to the obvious conclusion that the daily flow of requirements included in the maintenance and repair system can vary within:

$$\bar{N}_e = N_c \pm \sqrt{N_{ci}} \quad (5)$$

This circumstance indicates the need to take into account possible fluctuations in the flow of requirements in the design and organization of maintenance and repair systems.

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